

Synthesis and EPR spectral studies on oxovanadium(IV) complexes of some oximes

Sulekh Chandra*, Usha Bansal, Sunita Gupta and Sunil Dutta Sharma

Department of Chemistry, Zakir Husain College, JLN Marg, New Delhi-110 002, India

E-mail: amit1984@mantraonline.com

Manuscript received 21 August 2000, revised 16 April 2001, accepted 16 June 2001

Oxovanadium(IV) complexes with some oximes, viz. 2-hydroxyacetophenone (hapo), 2-hydroxypropiofenone (hppo), 2-hydroxybutyrophenone (hbpo) and *o*-vanilin (ov) have been synthesized. Spectral evidence support a five-coordinate square-pyramidal geometry around vanadium. EPR spectra of the complexes have been recorded. The bonding coefficients have been calculated and discussed.

The metal complexes of *o*-hydroxyoximes received considerable attention due to structural features that are of general interest^{1,2}. These features include short intramolecular hydrogen bonds and packing configuration that give rise to unusual optical properties. The detailed study of such features and the correct explanation of these unusual properties are independent of precise structural information. The chemistry of these oximes is important in view of their possible application as biochemical models³ and as semiconducting materials⁴. Here we report oxovanadium(IV) complexes with some oximes, viz. 2-hydroxyacetophenone (hapo), 2-hydroxypropiofenone (hppo), 2-hydroxybutyrophenone (hbpo) and *o*-vanilin (ov). Square-pyramidal complexes of general composition VO (ligand-H)₂ are formed in each case. EPR spectra of the complexes have been studied in detail and the various bonding coefficients evaluated and discussed.

- (a) R = CH₃, X = H
(b) R = C₂H₅, X = H
(c) R = C₃H₇, X = H
(d) R = H, X = OCH₃

Results and Discussion

Elemental analysis data reveal the complexes to have general composition VO(ligand-H)₂ (Table 1). The magnetic moments of the complexes lie in the range 1.65–1.70 B.M., which are in range observed for oxovanadium(IV) complexes having completely quenched orbital contribution⁵.

IR spectra of the ligands showed a strong band at 3450–3475 cm⁻¹ (phenolic OH). The absence of this band in the spectra of their complexes suggests coordination through

the oxygen of the phenolic group. Another strong ligand band at 1580–1590 cm⁻¹ (C=N) shifted to lower frequency (~25 cm⁻¹) in the spectra of the complexes, suggesting involvement of this group in chelation. Some new bands also appeared in the spectra of the complexes at ~990 (V=O) 460–475 (M–O) and 393–398 cm⁻¹ (M–N).

Table 1 Colour, isotropic contact term and binding coefficients parameters of the complexes*

Compd	Colour	K	(β ₂ [*]) ²	(β ₁ [*]) ²	(eπ [*]) ²
VO(hapo) ₂	Orange	0.760	0.946	0.550	0.650
VO(hppo) ₂	Orange	0.764	0.898	0.590	0.514
VO(hbpo) ₂	Purple	0.758	0.972	0.608	0.680
VO(ov) ₂	Orange	0.761	0.970	0.615	0.682

*All the complexes gave satisfactory V, C, H and N analyses

Three spin-allowed transition, viz. ²B₂ → ²E₁ (ΔE₂), ²B₂ → ²B₁ (ΔE₁), ²B₂ → ²A₁ (ΔE₃) are expected for such complexes⁶, respectively around 13000, 16000 and 26000 cm⁻¹. The ΔE₃ transition is of higher energy and usually obscured by intense low-lying charge transfer and inter-ligand transitions. In the present studies, spectra of the complexes displayed two bands at 17200–17400 and 19000–19400 cm⁻¹, which may be assigned to ²B₂ → ²E₁ (ΔE₂) and ²B₂ → ²B₁ (ΔE₁) transitions, respectively⁷.

EPR spectra of these complexes have been recorded as polycrystalline samples in chloroform solutions at room temperature and at liquid nitrogen temperature. EPR signals are observed for oxovanadium complexes because of the lower symmetry, which results in a longer relaxation time⁸. Spectra of the polycrystalline samples gave one signal in each case. As expected the *g*-values are invariably lower than the free-electron value (*g*_e = 2.0023). This lowering is related to the spin-orbit interaction of the ground state, *d*_{xy} level with low lying excited states. In chloroform solutions, eight line isotropic spectrum resulted at room temperature due to isotropic intramolecular dipolar

interactions between the electrons ($S = 1/2$) and the vanadium ($I = 7/2$). No super hyperfine splitting were observed. This indicates that the unpaired electrons to be in $B_{2g}(d_{xy})$ orbital localized on the metal, thus excluding any possibility of its direct interactions with the incoming ligands. In the frozen solution, the spectra are anisotropic and the types of resonance components, one set due to parallel features and the other set due to perpendicular features, were observed. The principal components of the g and A tensors were calculated from the observed spectra and are tabulated in Table 2. The g -values in solutions are also lower than the free electron value ($g_e = 2.0023$). The lowering is related to the spin-orbit interaction of the ground state, d_{xy} level with low-lying excited states. Thus lowering from g_e is also an approximate measure of the ligand field strength. But the ΔE and g -values are not directly related since change in orbital coefficients influences the g -values. Also the hyperfine coupling constants are related to the direct dipolar term P (dipole-dipole interaction of electron moment and nuclear moment) and to an indirect dipolar interaction caused by the anisotropy in g -values. From experimental results we can calculate the values of $(\beta_2^*)^2$, A_{\parallel} and A_{\perp} are taken to be negative. Values of P are chosen to be $+136 \text{ G}^9$. The g -expression and energy term ΔE_1 and $(\beta_2^*)^2$ can be calculated. A value of 170 cm^{-1} is assumed for spin-orbit coupling constant. The calculated values are given in Table 1. Boucher *et al.*¹⁰ in a survey of EPR and spectral properties of oxovanadium complexes of a variety of ligands have shown an empirical linear relationship between A_0 , $(g_e - g_0)$ and $(g_e - g_{\parallel})$. It has been demonstrated that as A_0 increases both $(g_e - g_0)$ and $(g_e - g_{\parallel})$. The origin of the isotropic contact term k , which is related to the amount of unpaired electron density on the vanadium nucleus, has been subject of discussion. Since the orbital that contains the unpaired electron d_{xy} has zero electron density at the vanadium nucleus does not mix metal $4s$ orbital, there is no direct way of putting unpaired electron density on the nucleus. The non-zero value of k must then arise from the indirect mechanism.

Table 2. EPR parameters of the complexes

Compd.	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	g_0	A_{\parallel}	A_{\perp}	A_0
VO(hapo) ₂	1.966	1.988	1.987	172.6	60.3	97.73
VO(hppo) ₂	1.968	1.994	1.985	173.2	64.5	100.73
VO(hbpo) ₂	1.962	1.992	1.982	179.8	66.6	104.33
VO(ov) ₂	1.969	2.002	1.991	176.2	62.7	100.53

The value of the in-plane σ -bonding coefficient $(\beta_1^*)^2$ generally follows the donor σ strength of the ligand, i.e. $(\beta_1^*)^2$ decreases as the covalent bonding increases. This parameter shows comparatively larger variation, 0.5 to 0.615 in the present complexes. The dependence of k on $(\beta_1^*)^2$ arises from the participation of the empty $4s$ orbitals on the metal in σ -bonding to the ligands. The empty $4s$ orbital on the metal can overlap with the filled J -levels of the basal ligands as effectively as can be $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital of the

metal. The MO formed from the $4s$ orbitals should put partial $4s$ density in a filled bonding orbital which in turn should undergo spin-polarization by the d_{xy} electron. The extent of the ligand to the metal interaction should be related to both energy of antibonding $d_{x^2-y^2}$ energy level and its orbital coefficient. The $4s$ contribution to k should be proportional to the metal electron density to the filled orbital that contains the contribution of the $4s$ orbitals. The delocalization in the σ -system of the complexes in expressed by the bonding coefficients for the $d_{x^2-y^2}$ level.

Since the change in the $(\beta_2^*)^2$ is small, the major change in k for the less covalently bound complexes must be due to the $4s$ σ -bonding effect¹¹. The energy separation of the bonding and antibonding orbital for the $4s$ ligand interaction is inversely proportional to the indirect $4s$ contribution to k . This energy separation should be a function of the in-plane ligand reflected in ΔE_1 in the electronic absorption spectra.

- The most interesting observation in the present set of data is that $(\beta_1^*)^2$ and $(\beta_2^*)^2$ show opposite trends. The bonding coefficient $(e\pi^*)^2$, for the d_{xz} and d_{yz} orbits measures the covalency of the V=O. It also indirectly shows the strength of the in-plane ligands, since stronger the in-plane donor atom, the less covalent is the V=O bond.

Solvent effect: The geometry of the oxovanadium complexes is such that a sixth ligand molecule can readily be added to the vanadium along the Z -axis *trans* to the axial oxygen. Although weak the interaction enthalpy is still substantial (-5 to $-10 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$). Good donor solvents should then be added to the vanadium and increased the ligand field strength along the Z -axis. In agreement with this, infrared spectral measurements have shown that V=O is markedly lowered by the interaction with the strong N donor solvent pyridine. EPR parameters for the complexes in a number of solvents are given in Table 3. Within experimental error, the g_0 values do not vary. The A_0 values vary over a wide range ($\Delta A \sim 2-4 \text{ G}$). The higher values of A_0 are found for the complexes in non-coordinating solvents like benzene, toluene and xylene than in poorly coordinating solvents like chloroform and methylenechloride.

Table 3. EPR parameters of complexes in various solvents

Solvents	VO(hapo) ₂		VO(hppo) ₂		VO(hbpo) ₂	
	g_0	A_0	g_0	A_0	g_0	A_0
Benzene	1.969	106	1.965	105	1.959	106
Acetone	1.986	103	1.988	106	1.984	104
Chloroform	1.986	104	1.982	104	1.986	102
Methylene chloride	1.952	102	1.952	103	1.989	104
Toluene	1.998	105	-	-	1.989	106
Xylene	1.996	105	-	-	1.986	106

Experimental

All the ligands were synthesized by the reported method¹².

Preparation of the complexes :

A mixture of hot aqueous solution (30 ml) of vanadyl sulfate (0.05 mol) and hot ethanolic solution of the respective ligand (0.1 mol) was refluxed for 1 h on a water-bath and then cooled. The resulting solid complexes were washed with ethanol and dried over P₄O₁₀ in vacuum desiccator.

Magnetic susceptibility was measured at room temperature on a CAHN-2000 Faraday balance using Hg[Co(CNS)]₄ ($\chi_g = 16.44 \times 10^{-6}$ g/cc at 28°) as calibrating agent. Molar conductance was measured on a Leeds Northrup 4995 conductivity bridge. IR spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu IR-435 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra (nujol) on a Hitachi-300 spectrophotometer and EPR spectra on a Varian E4 EPR spectrometer using DPPH as marker. C, H and N were analysed at Microanalytical Laboratory, University Science Instrumentation Centre, Delhi University, Delhi.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Department of Science & Technology, New Delhi, for financial assistance and to Principal, Zakir Husain Collage, Delhi University, Delhi, for facilities.

References

1. Y. N. Kukushkin, M. V. Bovina, A. V. Zinchenko, V. K. Belsky and V. Y. Kukushkin, *Polyhedron*, 1997, **16**, 2494; K. H. Reddy and Y. Lingappa, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1994, **19**, 487, M. M. Aly and N. I. A. Shatti, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1996, **21**, 361; Y. Gok, S. Karabock and M. N. Mishra, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1998, **23**, 333; Y. Gok and H. Kantekin, *Polyhedron*, 1997, **16**, 2413.
2. A. A. Razik and A. K. A. Hadi, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1994, **19**, 84.
3. D. G. Brown, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1973, **18**, 177; G. N. Schrauzer, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1976, **15**, 417
4. T. W. Thomas and A. E. Underhill, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 1972, **1**, 99; A. E. Underhill, D. M. Watkins and R. Pethig *Inorg. Nucl. Chem. Lett.*, 1973, **9**, 1269.
5. A. T. Casey, B. S. Morris, E. Sinn and J. R. Thackeray, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1972, **25**, 1195; G. O. Garlisle and D. A. Crutchfield, *Inorg. Nucl. Chem. Lett.*, 1972, **8**, 554.
6. J. R. Wasson and H. J. Stocklosa, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1974, **36**, 227; C. J. Ballhausen and H. B. Gray, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, **1**, 111; J. Bernal and P. H. Reiger, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1963, **2**, 256; R. M. Golding, *Mol. Phys.*, 1962, **5**, 369.
7. J. Selbin, G. Maus and D. L. Johnson, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1967, **29**, 1735; K. M. Jones and E. Larson, *Acta Chim Scand.*, 1965, **19**, 1210; L. J. Boucher, E. C. Tynan and T. F. Yen, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, **7**, 731.
8. N. S. Garifyanov and V. N. Fodotov, *Zh. Strukt. Khim.*, 1962, **3**, 711; *Dokl. Akad. Nauk. SSSR*, 1964, **155**, 385.
9. N. B. Kalinichenko, I. N. Marov, A. N. Ermakov and Yu. I. Dubro, *Zh. Neorg. Khim.*, 1973, **18**, 2861.
10. L. J. Boucher, E. C. Tynan and T. F. Yen in "Electron Spin Resonance of Metal Complexes", ed. T. F. Yen, 1969.
11. B. R. McGarvey, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1964, **41**, 3743.
12. A. I. Vogel, "Practical Organic Chemistry", ELBS, London, 1973.